

ONE4ALL PROJECT

WHAT HAPPENED IN THE FIRST SIX MONTHS

Sites technical inspections for ONE4ALL demonstrators

How can the robot interact with the production environment?

How can the robots interact with employees?

How to guarantee safe collaboration among humans and machines?

Which technology solution is most adequate, and which are the technical limitations (space, ambient conditions, ecc...) that must be overcome?

To give an answer to these questions, the technical partners of the Consortium have organised 2 inspections in the companies selected for the demonstration of project solutions; the information and data gathered have been analysed by the technology providers ([Automationware](#), [Idener](#) and [Innogloba](#)) and contributed to the writing of public Deliverable D4.1 “*RCPM specifications, prototype version and tests foreseen*”.

This document provides an overview of the robotic solutions proposed for the end-user demonstrators selected in the agri-food sector ([Madama Oliva](#)) and in the pharmaceutical sector ([Orifarm](#)).

This deliverable, once approved by the European Commission, will be published on the project website, at [this page](#)

The ethical management of a Horizon Europe project

The framework programme of Horizon Europe contains binding principles and rules dealing with inclusion and ethics. The academic partner [TU Dortmund University](#) has adapted these guidelines to the specific aspects of ONE4ALL project, expressed in the public deliverable D7.7 “*Report on gender and ethical issues in the ONE4ALL project*”.

The topics of research integrity, data protection and privacy, artificial intelligence, health and safety as well as environmental protection are addressed within the report, as well as gender and inclusion-related aspects.

Moreover, on May 25th TU Dortmund University has organised a webinar on “gender and ethics for the management of project activities” for the partners, to better introduce these topics, gather initial information and comments, for monitoring these indicators during the whole project.

The mentioned deliverable, once approved by the European Commission, will be published on the project website, at [this page](#)

ONE4ALL Project at the Eurosim Congress

From 3rd to 5th July, [Karlsruhe Institute of Technology](#) attended the [XI Eurosim Congress](#) in Amsterdam, representing ONE4ALL project.

To disseminate the first project’s findings, the partner has summarized the research results into 2 posters, displaying the possible implementations of Digital Twins for sustainable manufacturing.

These literature reviews have been conducted in the frame of ONE4ALL project, involving some of the technical partners.

[Want to know more about the project?](#)

More details on the project activities, results, consortium are available on the official website: <https://one4allproject.eu/>

To remain updated, follow ONE4ALL social medias: [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#)